

APPLICATION OF BAYESIAN THEOREM IN RETROSPECTIVE VALIDATION OF RUBRICS OF NUX VOMICA USING SYNTHESIS REPERTORY.

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ABSTRACT

Bayes' Theorem calculates the likelihood of an event. For diagnostic purposes, conditional probability is also helpful in the medical sciences. By following Bayes' theorem, the scientific value of homoeopathy can be re-evaluated. Bayes theorem suggests that relative incidence should be used instead of absolute occurrence while compiling symptoms to our Materia medica. The Bayes theorem is applicable to both prospective and retrospective research as well as to consensus based on a large number of examples. In experience-based systems, like homoeopathy, confirmation bias is a significant source of erroneous data. This is something that homoeopathic practitioners should be aware of, and long case follow-ups could be able to fix it. However, it may be overcome by analysing rubrics prospectively using likelihood ratio. The absolute grading method of homoeopathic repertories poses a significant danger to reliability (LR). Here, we'll go over the literature that has already been published and the work that has been done to validate the rubrics taken from the existing repertory using the Bayes theorem.

KEYWORDS:

Bayes theorem, Bayesian theorem, Homeopathy, Repertory, Synthesis, Validation, Rubric.

INTRODUCTION

Repertory is an index of symptoms of Materia Medica, neatly arranged in a practical form and indicating the relative gradation of drugs, and it greatly facilitates for quick selection of the indicated remedy. (Tiwari, 2012)

In Dr. Hahnemannian era there were almost 100 medications which were successfully proven. But as the time passed it became difficult for him to keep the record of all the symptoms as the remedies expanding and even the proving's. Master Hahnemann was aware of the need for indexing of these all expanding collection of knowledge. Hahnemann identified that this expanding knowledge of Homoeopathic Materia medica was out of the capacity of human mind and hence there should be tool that can help in finding all this data. (Tiwari, 2012)

BACKGROUND AND JUSTIFICATION

- Homoeopathic medicines are graded based on occurrences in proving and casual clinical experience, despite being the most modern and improved Repertory with numerous additions and corrections from various authors. This absolute grading in place of relative ones without any consistent rule or qualification poses a serious threat to their reliability.
- Our repertoires rely on a solitary observation of a symptom manifesting in a case that has been proven or "cured," meaning that the symptoms must be present. This is a deliberate and dangerous error; a symptom is only a sign for a particular medication if it affects individuals who are responding well to it more often than other patients.
- Relying solely on the expertise of a single expert, which contributes to some of the limitations of repertory; additionally, a portion of the problems arise from failing to compare the prevalence of a medicine-cured population with the general population.
- Furthermore, there is a notable discrepancy between the severity of the repertory rubrics and the frequency of symptoms. Large rubrics usually contain unnecessary entries, but short rubrics usually

do not include any medications. However, this structural defect may be fixed by employing assessment rubrics and systematic analysis with the Bayes theorem and likelihood ratio (LR), which produce a fair assurance that the prescribed medication would work in the prescribed condition. The grade should be based on the differences between the general population and the medical population. According to the Bayes theorem, a treatment's likelihood of effectiveness rises if a symptom is experienced more frequently than not by patients who receive the treatment

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

STUDY SETTING:

All the records of patients were collected from various OPD's in Bharati Vidyapeeth Homoeopathic Hospital, Pune, investigated and examined by experienced homoeopathic physicians were taken for this study.

STUDY DESIGN:

A Retrospective observational study in already registered cases with Nux Vomica remedy prescription by various homoeopathic physicians in various OPDs of Bharati Vidyapeeth Homoeopathic Hospital within last 5 years were taken for study after taking permission from hospital administration.

LR was calculated by analysing and repertorizing the case and rubrics from synthesis repertory. GHOS (Glasgow Homoeopathic Hospitals Outcome scale) or ORIDL (Outcome in Relation to Impact on Daily Living) scale was taken for assessing all the cases in the study. Mainly GHOS scale was used for assessing the cases. 9-point scale was used to calculate the outcome of all the cases.

CASE DEFINITION:

Total 226 cases which were already registered within the age group of 18-65 years old, both sexes, acute or chronic which were fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria were considered. Data was recorded assessing the symptoms at the 1st visit of patients and the outcome at the end.

SELECTION OF SAMPLE:

Study design- Observational study.

Type of research- Retrospective study.

Sample size- 200 - 400 registered cases.

Selection criteria- on the basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Sample method- required statistical tools were used & patient's confidentiality was maintained.

SELECTION OF MEDICINE:

Nux vomica is an important polychrest remedy prepared from poison nut. It is used mainly after over dose of any medicine. Mainly has its action on gastro-intestinal tract. According to William Boerick Materia medica "Nux vomica is suited to active, irritable, nervous, over working individuals." The individuals of Nux vomica are irritable, angry, workaholic, industrious. They are usually dictatorial, doesn't want to be touched or are very revered, silent persons. Likes to be alone and do their work day and night. Like night watching, are of fault-finding nature. Headache due to late night work load, alcohol, tobacco, any type of exertion usually mental exertion. Has watery type of coryza during daytime and stuffed feeling in nose at night.

There are severe episodes of nausea, vomiting but cannot vomit out. Vomiting due to over exertion, alcohol, tobacco, etc. Flatulence and abdominal pain. Has constipated alternating with diarrhoea, constipations with ineffectual urging and straining for stools.

SELECTION OF RUBRICS:

Frequently repeated and prominent symptoms of the selected cases were converted into rubrics using Synthesis Repertory which were considered for the study. Total 16 rubrics were taken for the study, some of them were general rubrics of the remedy Nux vomica and some were keynotes of the same.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- i. Patients within the age group of 18- 65 years were taken for the study.
- ii. All types of cases whether acute or chronic cases were taken for the study
- iii. Prescriptions with only one single remedy (Nux Vomica) were considered.
- iv. Cases of Both sexes were included in the study.
- v. Cases following the ORIDL/GHHOS scale were considered.
- vi. Cases that can be repertorized using Synthesis Repertory were considered.
- vii. Acute cases included in the study; outcomes recorded at the last follow up were considered for analysis.
- viii. Chronic cases were considered in the study, with minimum 2 follow ups.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Prescriptions with more than one medicine were excluded.
2. Patients below the age of 18 years and above 65 years, as homogenous and comparable data cannot be obtained.
3. Cases not following ORIDL scale were excluded.
4. Cases not having follow up were not considered.

DURATION OF STUDY:

Study was carried out in a duration of 18 months.

DATA COLLECTION TOOL:

The ORIDL (Outcome In Relation To Impact on Daily Life) scale was used for assessing the condition of the patient also known as GHHOS. 9 – point scale was used for assessing the outcome of the case and is mentioned below.

- +4 = Cures / back to normal
- +3 = Major improvement
- +2 = Moderate improvement affecting daily living
- +1 = slight improvement, no effect on daily living 0 - no change/ unsure
- 1 = slight deterioration, no effect on daily living
- 2 = moderate deterioration, affecting daily living
- 3 = major deterioration
- 4 = disastrous deterioration

DATA COLLECTION SHEET:

All the necessary relevant data for study in every case with follow-ups was analysed using the GHHOS scale. Attention was paid to anamnesis (classical seeking), each symptom and its associated modalities, the circumstances related to the appearance of the symptoms that are ailments from, the mental and physical generals, using the strong characteristics, the acuteness of the senses of each patient, a special consideration was taken and were then recorded directly in Microsoft Excel Sheets as mentioned below.

1. Registration number of the patient.
2. Date of the first visit
3. Name of the patient.
4. Gender/Age
5. System involved/Complaints
6. Medicine
7. Outcome
8. Rubrics

BRIEF PROCEDURE:

All the selected symptoms and rubrics of cases were assessed and repertorized from synthesis repertory from the selected population for this retrospective observational study. ORIDL scale was used for

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assessing the outcome of each case and the last follow up was taken for assessment. In this study, all the chronic cases with minimum 2 follow ups were taken for assessment. Every case record was studied through direct observation and then recorded on the MS Excel Sheet.

Symptom related to a medicine and its LR was calculated as follows:

$LR = \frac{\text{Prevalence of the symptom in the population responding to the target medicine}}{\text{Prevalence of the symptom in the rest of the patient}}$

As per GHHOS scale symptoms calculating LR of the symptoms, 3-point scale is used (0, +2, +4). All the symptoms were assessed on the basis of 3 degrees mentioned below:

0 = absent

1 = mild/less intense

2 for strong indication.

Grade 1 absence of symptoms

Grade 2 mild or symptom intensity is less, but is considered after consumption of medicine

Grade 3 strong and spontaneous occurrence

LR was calculated according to the 2x2 contingency table, where

i. Number of patients with a certain symptom improved by Nux Vomica

ii. "Remainder of study sample" presenting with the symptom. (Suman Bagchi, 2018)

iii. Number of patients with absence of the symptom, still improved by the medicine; and (Suman Bagchi, 2018)

iv. "Remainder of the study sample" not having the symptom. (Suman Bagchi, 2018)

When LR is large, CI is taken to be 95%. The "p" value indicates the likelihood that the medicine's LR value would be fulfilled, and the correction of the medication and its symptoms was carried out using a grade system that uses bold, italic, and roman typeface.

OUTCOME ASSESSMENT:

Difference between population which is expressed by Bayesian theorem as LIKELIHOOD RATIO and medicine is indicated through synthesis repertory.

CAPITAL typeface is indicated when LR is higher or more than and equal to 6.

The table 2 presented next will tell us the possible schema for translation of LR into FACETYPE.

TYPE LIKELIHOOD RATIO

Plain/roman-1.5 to 2.9

Italics-3.0 to 4.0

Bold small-4.0 to 6.0

BOLD CAPITAL-More than 6

LR. 6 and $p < 0.1$

LR. 4 and $p < 0.1$

LR.3 and $p < 0.1$

LR.1.5 and $p < 0.1$

The medicine is discarded from the pick list if the LRs < 1 and for discarding the symptom, $LR < 1$ and $p < 0.1$

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES AND DATA ANALYSIS:

Microsoft Excel programme was used to analysed and evaluate the data in the study. The prevalence, LR+ with 95% confidence interval and LR- with 95% confidence interval were calculated in the study. MS excel was used for all the calculation in the study. MEDCALC For the calculation of p-value (area under the curve) was further calculated through SPSS using Chi square test. Different forms of descriptive statistics like the pivot tables, pie charts, pivot charts, and the bar-charts for analyzing the results of this study.

ETHICAL ISSUES:

For conducting of study prior permission from the ethical committee. For collection of all the case papers, recorded during the time duration of January 2017 to December 2021, approval was taken from hospital superintendent and hospital administrator. Total 226 case were recorded after proper

evaluation and analysis retrospectively. Confidentiality of all the personal information of the patient was kept intact during the study and the study does not report over the primary data.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT:

After removing the instances that did not meet the inclusion criteria for the retrospective analysis, 226 cases were evaluated. Nux Vomica-prescribed cases were evaluated. The distribution of the 226 cases age distribution pattern, the total number of cases per year, and the number of patients experiencing complaints from various systems are all described. The GHHOS scale, which has nine points, was used to determine the case outcome.

The intensity was noted on the basis of degree with which they were present,

0: denotes the absence of the symptom,

1: denotes the presence of the symptom in low intensity and

2: denotes the presence of symptom in higher intensity.

Expressing the relative incidence of the rubrics into the form of LR:

Rubric	Prevalence	Typeface	Expected LR+	Assessed LR+
MIND- Irritability	5.3%	Bold small	>4	1.07
NOSE- Coryza	4.0%	Bold small	>4	1.15
STOMACH- Acidity	75.8%	Bold small	>4	7.77
STOMACH- Nausea	76.2%	Bold small	>4	6.59
STOMACH-Eructation; Type of -sour	15.9%	Bold small	>4	1.08
STOMACH- Vomiting	75.3%	Italics	>3	6.11
STOMACH- Pain, epigastrium, in	26.4%	Italics	>3	1.01
CHEST- Pain, burning	9.3%	Italics	>3	1.11
ABDOMEN- Distension	9.8%	Italics	>3	1.06
HEAD- Pain, forehead	29.5%	Bold small	>4	1.13
ABDOMEN- Flatulence	19.4%	Italics	>3	1.21
STOOL- Hard	69.6%	Bold small	>4	3.24
RECTUM- Constipation, insufficient	72.7%	Bold small	>4	3.12
RECTUM- Constipation- ineffectual urging and straining	70.9%	Bold small	>4	3.05
STOOL- Watery	7.6%	Bold small	>4	1.15
ABDOMEN- Pain	79.3%	Italics	>3	3.04

Table 1: Expected and assessed occurrences of the rubrics of Nux vomica along with the prevalence%

Total 16 Rubrics were considered for evaluating the typeface of Nux Vomica as mentioned in the Synthesis Repertory.

- For Rubrics “STOMACH- Acidity”- (LR+7.77, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:3.89-15.52) STOMACH- Nausea” - (LR+6.59, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:3.48-12.51) Nux Vomica is present as bold small typeface. But after following our assessment these two rubrics should be placed in BOLD CAPITAL typeface and p-value in these symptoms is highly significant which can be a indicate to justify the existing the typeface.

- For Rubric “STOMACH- Vomiting” - (6.11, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:3.36-11.13) Nux Vomica is present in italic typeface. Following what our assessment suggests, this rubric “STOMACH- Vomiting” should be placed in BOLD CAPITAL typeface and p-value in these symptoms is highly significant which can be a indicate to justify the existing the typeface.

- For the Rubric “NOSE- Coryza” (LR+1.15, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:0.90-1.46) Nux Vomica

is placed in Bold small but our assessment suggests that it should be placed under Roman typeface, but p-value is insignificant so its entry is still doubtful.

- For the Rubric “STOMACH- Eructations; Type of – sour” (LR+1.08, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:0.92-1.28) Nux Vomica is placed in Bold small but our assessment suggests that it should be placed under Roman typeface, but p-value is insignificant so its entry is still doubtful.
- For Rubrics “STOOL- Hard” - (LR+3.24, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:2.27-4.64), “RECTUM- Constipation, insufficient” - (LR+3.12, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:2.15-4.55) and “RECTUM- Constipation- ineffectual urging and straining” (LR+3.05, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:2.14-4.34) Nux vomica is placed under Bold small (LR+>4) but our assessment suggests that Nux Vomica should be placed under italics typeface (LR+>3), p-value in these symptoms is highly significant which can be an indication to justify the existing typeface.
- Nux Vomica for the rubrics “MIND- Irritability” (LR+ 1.07, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:0.21-2.71) is mentioned under Bold small typeface but after assessing it should be placed under roman typeface, but p-value is insignificant so its entry is still doubtful.
- Nux Vomica for the rubrics “STOMACH- Pain, epigastrium, in” (LR+ 1.01, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:0.86-1.18); “CHEST- Pain, burning” (LR+ 1.11, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:0.92-1.35) and “ABDOMEN- Distension” (LR+ 1.06, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:0.86-1.31), Nux vomica is placed under italics typeface in the synthesis repertory but as per our assessment Nux Vomica for these rubrics must be downgraded into roman typeface or discarded with caution after study with large population size.
- For the Rubrics “ABDOMEN- Flatulence” (LR+ 1.21, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:1.07-1.38) Nux vomica is placed under italics typeface in synthesis repertory but after assessment it should be downgraded into roman typeface, p-value in these symptoms is highly significant which can be an indication to justify the existing typeface.
- Rubric “ABDOMEN- Pain” (LR+ 3.04, 95% Confidence Interval [CI]:1.96-4.73) is mentioned under italics typeface in synthesis repertory and even after our assessment it should be considered as italics typeface, even the p-value in these symptoms is highly significant which can be an indication to justify the existing typeface.

DISCUSSION:

One of the most common and often prescribed medications is Nux Vomica. Although some are still dubious, doctors are already aware that there are symptoms in a case that calls for a prescription for Nux Vomica. Reliability regarding the relationship between the medication and the symptoms is necessary to improve the prescription. Several contemporary statistical techniques, such as the Bayesian Analysis utilising LR, must be used in order to validate homoeopathy and provide it with more trustworthy, substantiated proof.

There is threat to the reliability of our repertories without considering LR methodology and Bayes Theorem statistics. Purpose of my study was an attempt to add a new entry and even to discard an already existing entry of a Homoeopathic Remedy Nux vomica in Synthesis Repertory with statistical reasoning. In contrast, a high LR of the symptom is required to confirm a medication, but a high prevalence of a symptom could lead to its discarding in the absence of that symptom. Using the chi-squared test and 2x2 contingency tables with Yates continuity correction, the "p" value was determined.

Symptom prevalence was calculated by the formula $a/a+c$, where:

- “a”: complaints improved by Nux vomica with presence of that symptom.
- “c”: complaints improved by Nux vomica with absence of that symptom.

95% CI was calculated with the aid of MEDCALC (medcalc.org), and “p” value was calculated using SPSS-IBM software.

Total 16 rubrics of Nux vomica commonly prescribed were assessed retrospectively with help of statistical reasoning to evaluate the typeface existing in the synthesis repertory which is most frequently used by Homoeopathic physicians.

The study was made to learn the relation between Nux vomica and its symptoms. The main purpose of this study was to calculate the likelihood ratio and prevalence of frequently prescribed homeopathic remedy Nux vomica.

Total of 226 cases from the records were collected from last five years, excluding the cases which were not matching the inclusion criteria. From the collected data, with prescription of Nux Vomica, 155 (68.58%) cases accounted for the female population whereas 71 (31.41%) accounted for the male population.

Out of 226 cases were prescribed with Nux Vomica 176 cases showed good results, and 50 cases were assessed as not responding to treatment given (prescribed with Nux Vomica). From the collected data for the study major of the cases were from Gastrointestinal system.

Symptoms responding well to Nux vomica were assessed by calculating their likelihood.

Total 16 rubrics were assessed in this study. For Rubrics “STOMACH- Acidity”; “STOMACH- Nausea” and “STOMACH-Vomiting” Nux Vomica is present as bold small typeface but should be upgraded to BOLD CAPITAL typeface.

While for “ABDOMEN- Pain” Rubrics it was found to be relevant with its existing typeface in Synthesis Repertory. And 11 rubrics could be downgraded but with caution, while 1 Rubric is still doubtful.

It is necessary to consider a number of shortcomings while evaluating the findings of the research. A variety of biases could affect the study and the data. It gets harder to pinpoint the patient's effective progression point during a retrospective study, which makes it more challenging to prescribe the medication and course of therapy.

Just because the symptom has been recorded in the case does not connote that the symptom was actually present in the patient and even the intensity isn't accurate or powerful enough so that it could be considered as a definitive indicator of that medicine. Few symptoms are left unnoticed or unrecorded by the physician. The inference corresponds to higher prevalence rather than with LR.

CONCLUSION:

This undertaken research is mere a means to evaluate and assess the symptoms prevalence in the population with good response to Nux Vomica. This study doesn't aim at diagnosing the illness but it aims at increasing the accuracy for prescription of Nux Vomica. The importance of few Rubrics in the medicine must be upgraded.

There are flaws in our Repertories and in Synthesis Repertory as well, which can be further be corrected and rectified by implication of the Likelihood Ratio. Physicians are well acquainted with the main symptom and the symptoms which indicate directly to Nux vomica but this depends upon the prevalence of the symptom rather than the LR of the symptoms. Retrospective verification and assessment of symptom prevalence and LR in patients with good response can be a better way for selection of the symptom for a prospective study. The result obtained from the study, shows probable relation to the type face present in Synthesis Repertory for Nux vomica under Rubrics.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest.

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